

Best Practices for Diversifying the Faculty in the Sciences

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Introduction

In recent years, the student body has become much more diverse. Although institutions declare that they are dedicated to diversity as a matter of both excellence and equity, diversity in the faculty body has not kept pace. In fact, it has largely remained stagnant. Creating a culture of inclusion is no longer a mere exercise; it is an imperative. As such, we must pay careful attention to the mechanisms of institutional practice as well as to individual cognitive gender schemas and cognitive racial schemas.

This document describes steps and strategies for conducting faculty searches. The goal is to structure and streamline searches in a way that is more conducive to the advancement of under-represented groups. Department chairs, administrators, faculty, and search committee members should familiarize themselves with this information, intended to help attract large and diverse applicant pools for academic positions in the sciences.

While there is no one-size-fits-all approach to faculty diversification, the intent of this document is to provide promising practices that will aid our efforts. As our experiences and understandings continue to evolve, these guidelines may be customized and refined to suit the needs of individual units.

Definitions of Minority Faculty

The Federal definition of a minority is someone who “differs in race, religion or national origin from the dominant group” (National Archives, 2016). According to Equal Employment Opportunity Commission (EEOC), this includes American Indian or Alaskan Native, Black or African American, Hispanic or Latino/x, and Asian or Pacific Islander. The National Science Foundation (NSF) and the National Institute of General Medical Sciences (NIH) recognize that certain groups are not represented in science, engineering, and health-related fields in numbers proportional to their composition in the U.S. population: women, persons with disabilities, and the first three aforementioned racial and ethnic groups. At most institutions, underrepresented minority (URM) refers to racial and ethnic groups that are not well represented. To improve equity in the faculty body, it is both legal and appropriate to actively seek a more diverse pool of candidates. Thus, we should direct our attention to increasing the number of URM, disabled, and female faculty members in colleges and universities.

Applicant Pool Diversification

An inclusion strategy must be built into every facet of the search process if we are to make a positive impact. If diversity drops off in the early stages of the search, our plans for an equitable future will inevitably fail. It cannot be emphasized enough that department heads and search chairs be held accountable for strategic efforts toward a diverse faculty, especially before the search process begins in earnest. Each vacancy must be treated as if it is the only shot the institution will ever get to find and hire a prospect who will increase your department’s diversity.

Timing

Intensive preparation at the beginning stages of the search will make the biggest difference in hiring outcomes. Any and all preemptive strategies should be employed. Departments may build consensus around the focal areas of future hires to expedite the timeline. In doing so, they should also be specific about what the position would look like. It is also recommended that, if at all possible, department heads prepare a rough draft of the job description and position announcement before the search has been approved. Due to constraints placed upon us by early diversity publication deadlines and the time required for thorough application screenings, ads should be released almost immediately. Such preparation will help to move the search through channels of approval well in advance of the administrative bottleneck that inevitably occurs at this stage. Job offers need to go out sooner but the only way to achieve this is to get ahead of the pack from the very start.

Research and Data Analysis

The very first step is to identify the national pools of qualified candidates for the field (and for subfields, if necessary) in which you are considering hiring. Labor market resources available online include the NSB Science and Engineering Indicators and the NSF Survey of Earned Doctorates. Librarians are happy to help with tasks associated with identifying the available pool.

Each department should also determine the top producers of URM PhD candidates in the field to aid their searches. Diverse Issues in Higher Education provides an excellent tool to search by discipline.

In addition, it is recommended that job ads be individually coded to track exactly which postings were most successful in attracting diverse applicants.

Position Description and Announcement

Think carefully about the qualifications you list so that your job descriptions don't end up hurting your pipeline. Refer to qualifications as "preferred" unless they are essential to success. Otherwise, you risk restricting the pool of candidates unnecessarily. Distinguish between teaching needs and research needs. Define the position as broadly as possible to attract a larger pool of candidates. Consider only those candidates who meet all "required" qualifications.

It is possible to leverage free resources to minimize overall costs. For example, post jobs on the Onramps to Academia and the Association of Black Women in Higher Education websites and send broad announcements to minority degree-producing institutions.

Language Analysis

Language has a tremendous impact on diversity in the candidate funnel; different types of phrases attract different types of candidates. Aim for consistency through action words that accurately describe what is being done and eliminate unintentional bias in the language used. Utilize qualifiers or adjectives with care; they may cause potential applicants to self-select themselves out of consideration. For example, anyone who has been raised/socialized to downplay their expertise will be less likely to categorize themselves in assertive ways, even when they are very highly qualified.

There are online tools, such as the Gender Bias Calculator and the Gender Decoder, that can be used to evaluate bias in recommendation letters and job descriptions. It is important to keep language up to date and to maintain a repository of exemplars to be used as guidance. Third-party vendors can provide the service of analyzing and improving job descriptions for effective language and format. Some talent management systems have the ability to code and track individual job announcements, allowing units to evaluate the effectiveness of each in drawing the most diverse pool of job applications.

Diversity Statement

A boilerplate Equal Employment Opportunity diversity statement in job postings does nothing to foster a culturally sensitive environment and may even be interpreted as insincere. Specific and compelling language about diversity in job postings is both necessary and desirable. With a little creativity, the standard equal opportunity statement can be transformed into something meaningful.

In addition to teaching and research statements from candidates, include a required statement on diversity and inclusion as part of the job application. This ensures that diversity is integral to the institution's achievement of excellence. The statement should address the candidate's past experience, activities and future vision for contributing actively to diversity, equity, and inclusion. The purpose of the statement is to identify candidates who have professional skills, experience, and/or willingness to engage in activities that would enhance your institution's diversity efforts at micro, meso, and macro levels.

Soliciting Recommendations & Nominations

Standard position announcements in national publications do not go very far in broadening the applicant pool. Other methods will cost less but require more in the investment of time. However, such an investment will pay off in the end.

The best candidates often have a lot of options to choose from, so committees must work proactively to recruit prospects. A new mindset is required if there is to be a measurable change in hiring outcomes. Don't wait for the right people to come to you. Start thinking like an athletic coach. Go out and find the talent you need.

Identify a process for the campus community to assist with talent discovery. An online form is an excellent method. Encourage sources to also identify candidates who are promising but need more time.

Networking

Treat recruitment as an ongoing activity that is part of normal academic and professional life, rather than as a special occasion. Personal outreach is significantly more effective than any other tool for building and diversifying the applicant pool. According to MIT's Report on the Initiative for Faculty Race and Diversity, approximately 79% of non-URM faculty applied directly to MIT compared to 37% of URM faculty. "It is more often the case that a member of the department approached the prospective faculty member and actively encouraged/recruited his/her application" (Reif, 2010).

Incorporate recruitment networking into professional conference attendance by faculty. Look for sessions given by younger, up-and-coming researchers. Attend receptions hosted by special interest groups for female and minority scholars. Foster effective habits.

Ask faculty to reach out to professional societies to which they belong. Professional meetings are opportunities to scout for prospects. Watch for advanced grad students and post-docs who will soon be on the job market.

Connecting with Potential Applicants

Consider using your department's lecture or seminar series as an opportunity to bring potential future applicants to campus. This is a "low stakes" way to introduce them to the unit and to give them a chance to experience your institution firsthand.

Scan peer institution departmental websites to read faculty profiles. Many have biographical information, publications, research interests, and possibly their entire vitae online. Consider reaching out to junior colleagues who may be currently under-placed at less well-ranked institutions or public universities. Search for promising candidates in directories, such as:

- Southern Regional Education Board Compact for Faculty Diversity
- American Association of University Women Directory of Fellowship Recipients
- Directory of Ford Fellows
- Faculty for the Future
- Diversifying Higher Education Faculty in Illinois (DFI) program
- MIT, Directory of Science & Engineering Faculty in Selected Institutions of Higher Education
- Rice University Future Faculty Database
- The National Consortium for Graduate degrees for Minorities in Engineering and Science
- University of California President's Postdoctoral Fellowship Program Directory

Special Considerations

- Candidates mentioned early in the process will have a significant advantage, so it is important that early lists include women and minorities.
- Many excellent candidates need to be encouraged to apply, especially if they do not see themselves as a natural fit.
- When describing your institution and its surrounding community, be aware of who may or may not see themselves as included in that description.
- Placing ads in venues that specifically target women has been shown to increase the representation of women in STEM.

Search Committee Operations

The search committee is responsible for actively generating a diverse pool of applicants, as opposed to just tapping it. Therefore, the committee charge should emphasize equitable search practices with the goal of finding excellent prospects, including outstanding women and URM candidates for the position.

Committee Composition and Structure

Bear in mind that women and minorities are typically asked to do more service than majority males. Keep track of their service load and, if necessary, free them from less significant service tasks and/or compensate them in other ways.

Although it may seem obvious, be sure to avoid appointing the faculty member with the most at stake as the chair of the committee.

When there are no available women or minorities within a program to serve on a search committee, consider appointing someone from another department to serve as a member or as an ex officio advisor. In addition, the department chair might wish to serve as an ex officio member of the committee.

Establishing Ground Rules

Avoid any ambiguity, which can create confusion that only serves to hamper and delay the selection process at critical points. Ground rules can include any of the following:

- Consensus or votes. Are absentee votes allowed? Will the votes be open or confidential?
- The New York Times rule. Don't write anything in an email that you wouldn't want to see on the front page of a major newspaper.
- Documentation. Maintain complete records.
- Decorum. Turn off phones? Ensure that all points of view are heard.
- Evaluation scale. Be flexible and consistent. Whatever scale is chosen, all should agree to it.
- Expectations. Be explicit about attendance and confidentiality.

Documentation

Applicant tracking at each stage of the hiring process provides a system of checks and balances that can pinpoint where and how diversity efforts may have gone awry. Create a physical and/or electronic file that describes each candidate's progress (e.g., nominated, applied, reviewed, failed to meet minimum qualifications, shortlisted, eliminated, etc.) Notes should indicate specific job-related reasons for selection or non-selection.

Ensure that the file location is secure so that confidentiality is maintained throughout the search. A collaboration tool such as OneDrive or SharePoint is recommended.

Candidate Selection Criteria

The search committee should discuss selection criteria before reviewing applications to provide a consistent standard against which all candidates can be evaluated. Be specific about essential requirements without which an applicant will not be selected, no matter how impressive their qualifications in other areas.

If "culture fit" is a criterion for hiring, provide a concrete definition. Remember that culture fit is not the same as a "lunch test" (individuals with whom you would like to have lunch). Instead, consider a candidate's unique contribution to your department, including new research areas or technologies, geographic regions, style of work, intellectual or political viewpoints, and other dimensions needing improvement.

Applicant Review and Discussion

Determine whether your applicant pool includes a proportionately appropriate number of outstanding women and URM before winnowing the applicant pool. If not, consider taking active steps to obtain additional applicants.

Reviewing dossiers is very time consuming. If possible, all committee members should review all applications. If there are hundreds of applicants, the committee chair should read all applications and assign subsets to each committee member. Vary the pairings of committee members with dossiers so that you don't unwittingly create "mini-committees of two."

Winnowing the Lists

Screen to include candidates, especially diverse candidates, in the first round. Screening with the purpose of narrowing the pool may cause you to miss very attractive candidates. Look for all exciting applicants, even those "not quite right" for the current position.

If the information on an individual's CV is insufficient, contact the candidate to secure additional information or to clarify items.

When developing the "long list," ask departmental colleagues whether any strong candidates are missing from the list. Contact those who may not have applied and encourage them to do so.

Pay special attention to individuals just below the "long list" cutoff or applicants who excel in one or two criteria, but not necessarily all.

Consider multiple criteria ranking, which might be more effective for improving diversity than ranking on a single list. Create separate “short lists” based on different criteria, such as teaching, research potential, collaborative potential, record on diversity, mentoring capacity, etc. This helps mitigate “halo” effects that result from reliance on overall impressions rather than evidence-based judgments of established criteria. The final “short list” would consist of top candidates across different criteria.

Skype or Phone Interviews

Avoid eliminating a promising candidate too quickly by developing an “intermediate list” first. As an “intermediate” stage in the screening process, consider using video conferencing or phone interviews to allow initial contact with a larger number of diverse candidates.

Establish a consistent set of questions for each candidate and ask them in the same order. Provide the opportunity for a candidate to speak to their diversity-related experience and expertise. Determine in advance how the answers will be rated.

Cognitive Errors

There is a large body of work on how unconscious biases and errors of judgment influence our evaluation of scientific work and job candidates. In her book, *Faculty diversity: Removing the barriers*, Dr. JoAnn Moody has identified common errors that influence hiring decisions.

Special Considerations

- For phone interviews, be aware that interviewing with only auditory cues can be very difficult for some personal styles and may not easily conform to some cultural norms.
- Beware of “moving target syndrome,” or changing the position requirements as the search progresses to either include or exclude candidates.
- Imbalances of power among committee members can serve to silence some members while allowing others too much control over the search process. Without intending to, senior faculty may intimidate untenured faculty on the committee. Periodically, the chair should check in with untenured colleagues outside of official committee meetings about any concerns that they might not have been able to voice in the presence of senior faculty.
- Understand that many ethnic minorities have experienced greater obstacles to receiving research grants as well as publication opportunities in prestigious journals.
- Be careful of what can look like tokenism on the “short list” : one woman, one minority member, and an otherwise all-white, all-male group. Research shows that interviewers more fairly evaluate women and minorities when they are not alone in the candidate pool.
- Career paths for minorities may vary in comparison to majority groups.

On-campus Interviews

At this point, departmental colleagues may raise new issues beyond the criteria used by the search committee. Individuals may seek to promote or exclude candidates who they believe will strengthen or threaten their position. For these and many other reasons, developing a matrix from the beginning is strongly recommended. Of all the things you can do as a committee member, being consistent is arguably the most important duty. No matter how diverse your applicant pool, none of it will matter if you cannot offer fair treatment for all candidates throughout the search.

Before the Interview

Review the job description and reaffirm evaluation criteria before this stage begins. Send a welcome packet with information about your institution as well as a common set of instructions to help candidates prepare for their visit. Providing these resources helps to level the playing field and improves the quality of interactions because the candidates are well informed.

Identify all people and groups to be involved in the interview process and provide them with relevant information about the position: job description, necessary areas of inquiry, and a list of standard interview questions.

Ensure that all interviewers are familiar with legal guidelines regarding what questions should be avoided during an interview. Provide additional coaching for faculty involved in the interview phase as needed.

In discussions with a candidate in preparation for their visit, become familiar with the candidate's cultural and language background and confirm the correct pronunciation of their name. Prepare faculty and students interacting with candidates to remain culturally sensitive.

During the Visit

The campus visit is not just about finding the right person for the job, it is about cultivating relationships. To this end, be sure that all candidates receive equal treatment and that you use inclusive language. Every candidate is an opportunity for future collaboration.

During the interview, include questions that allow a candidate to speak to their diversity-related experience and expertise.

For the job talk, standardize the structure as much as possible. Have a clock in the room so that the candidates can monitor their own pace.

Record job talks to ensure that voting members who are absent can watch the video.

After the Interview

Maintain personal contact with prospective candidates, even if they decide not to come to your institution. They or someone they know may be interested in the future.

Encourage individual candidate evaluations within 24 hours of each visit. Everyone who interacted with the candidate should provide feedback that focuses on specific facets of the candidate's potential and performance to minimize implicit bias.

Refrain from engaging in collective candidate evaluations, as this leads the group to agree on the "likability" of a candidate before more thoughtful review can occur.

Making the Final Recommendations

Avoid discussing personal characteristics that are not job relevant or global evaluations unsupported by specific evidence.

Beware of placing excessive weight on the job talk, since it represents just one slice of an individual's portfolio and is not always the best source of data.

Consider submitting an unranked list of finalists to the department chair to allow more diverse candidates to remain in the running at the last stage.

Special Considerations

- During campus visits, introduce women and minority department members to all candidates, not just to women and minority candidates.
- Recognize differences in personal and household circumstances. Do not assume that one household type (e.g., a spouse and children) applies to any individual.
- While academics are often partnered with other academics, academic women are more often partnered with other academics than their male counterparts. Thus, disadvantages facing dual-career academic couples have a disproportionate impact on women. Arrange interviews or other opportunities for the spouse/partner as early in the hiring process as possible.

Review the Process Ex Post

Regardless of the results of your search, use the collected data to review the faculty recruitment process, including diversity outreach efforts. It is essential to evaluate the effectiveness of the search – acknowledging the various successes and failures along the way – so that lessons can be shared with future search committees. Consider keeping the names of minority and women candidates who were identified by the search committee as promising scholars on file so that they may be notified of future searches.

Data Reporting

In order to support hiring at the departmental level and to provide an ongoing system of checks and balances, it is recommended that the college or university monitor and report the following:

- The representation of women, persons with disabilities, and URM in the hiring pipeline, from application to offer.
- The representation of women, persons with disabilities, and URM tenure and promotion rates, on a yearly basis.
- Faculty salaries evaluated through an objective methodology (i.e., quintile analysis).
- University resources supporting individual faculty research programs, to ensure their equitable distribution across gender, ability, and race.

Conclusion

It is possible to make progress in the diversification of higher education faculty but it requires the implementation of strategic interventions at all stages of the faculty search. At every step, consider ways, however small, to interrupt the usual.

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The Faculty Search Process

Appendix B: Sample Faculty Search Process Timeline

PHASE 1: PREPARING

PHASE 2: RECRUITING

PHASE 4: VISITING

PHASE 5: CLOSING

PHASE 6: ONBOARDING

PHASE 7: DEBRIEFING

Appendix C: Minority Degree Producers Search Tool

Minority Degree Conferrals in the Continental U.S. 2014-2017
 Based on the top 100 Institutions Awarding Minority Degrees per Discipline

Sources: Carnegie Classifications 2015; Diverse: Issues In Higher Education analysis of U.S. DoE reports submitted by institutions.

An interactive search tool that can be used to identify institutions producing the most minority degree conferrals. Improve your unit's recruiting and outreach efforts by searching within the targeted discipline. This tool can be found here: https://public.tableau.com/views/MinorityPhDs2014-2017/Dashboard1?:embed=y&:display_count=yes

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